

Efficient assembly of novel indolo quinoxaline architectures utilizing isatin through condensation and cyclization process

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Abstract : An efficient and rapid protocol for the assemblage of quinoxaline architectures via condensation of *N*-alkylated isatin derivatives with *o*-phenylenediamine (OPDA) utilizing acetic acid as mild catalyst and the reaction accomplished in good yield.

Keywords : Quinoxaline, *o*-phenylenediamine, isatin.

Introduction

Heterocyclic compounds, in particular the nitrogen containing motifs play a significant role in the establishment of diverse biologically active molecules. Many of the synthetic strategies have been exploited for an efficient construction of substituted quinoxalines. In addition, these quinoxaline motifs were utilized for synthesizing wide variety of compounds with useful pharmacological activities viz. antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti HIV, antimicrobial, anticancer, antitumor, anticonvulsant, antimalarial, anti-amoebic and antioxidant activity etc.¹⁻¹⁰. Some of the representative compounds are used as fluorescent dyeing agent, electroluminescent materials, chemical switches and semiconductors¹¹⁻¹⁴. Also numerous methods and catalysts have been reviewed for the preparation of quinoxaline architectures¹⁵. In the present study, we have report the synthesis of novel quinoxaline derivatives.

Results and discussion

The structure of the quinoxaline compound was characterized by IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR, mass spectral data and elemental analyses. Exclusively, the compounds **15A** and **15BQ** were indicated for IR spectral data which corresponds to the aromatic and aliphatic CH stretching ap-

peared in the region of 3064, 2946, 2845 cm⁻¹ respectively. The N-C=O (1736 cm⁻¹), carbonyl group (1726 cm⁻¹), aromatic C=C stretching (1599 cm⁻¹), C=N (1607, 1580 cm⁻¹). The ¹H NMR spectra of the compounds **15A** and **15AQ** indicates the presence of three aliphatic methylene protons present at 1.44–1.87 ppm and 1.53–2.01 ppm as multiplets. The nitrogen attached methylene and bromine attached to methylene proton showed as triplet in the region of 3.65 ppm, 3.31 ppm and 4.51 ppm and 3.78 ppm respectively. In the compound **15A** the four aromatic methine protons are showed as doublet in 6.88 ppm, 7.03 ppm as triplet, 7.48–7.50 ppm and 7.53–7.56 ppm as multiplets respectively. The eight aromatic methine protons of quinoxaline is observed at 7.36–7.39, 7.67–7.71, 7.74–7.77, 7.46, 8.52, 8.15 and 8.33 ppm. Furthermore, the nitrogen attached two methylene protons present in compounds **15B** and **15BQ** were shown as triplet at 3.37 ppm and 4.47 ppm respectively. The ¹³C NMR spectra for the compounds **15A** and **15AQ** the nitrogen and bromine attached methylene carbon showed the corresponding peaks at 39.89, 33.46 ppm and 41.12, 33.35 ppm respectively. The corresponding peaks for two carbonyl carbon attached to aromatic ring for **15A** was observed at 158.11 and 183.47 ppm. Some of the representative quinoxaline compounds **15AQ** and **15BQ** as depicted in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Materials :

Chemicals used for the synthesis were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA) and Merck (India).

Synthesis of (1-(5-bromopentyl)indoline-2,3-dione) :

Isatin (1 mmol) and dibromoalkane (1.2 mmol) were dissolved in dry acetonitrile (20 ml), and 3 mmol of anhydrous K_2CO_3 was added to the reaction mixture was stirred under reflux temperature. Disappearance of isatin was monitored continuously by thin layer chromatography. Further, the solvent is removed by applying vacuum and the resulting mixture was purified by column chromatography (hexane/ethyl acetate = 9 : 1). Finally, the *N*-alkyl substituted isatin and bisisatin compounds were obtained in 71% and 24% yield respectively.

Synthesis of (6-(5-bromopentyl)-6*H*-indolo[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline) :

Mixture of 1-(5-bromopentyl)-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione (1 mol), *o*-phenylenediamine (1 mol) and acetic acid (20 ml) was stirred under reflux 4 h. The solid was formed after cooling the reaction mixture further the resulting product was collected, washed with acetic acid (3 × 5 mL), and recrystallized from acetic acid.

Physico-chemical characteristics :

Melting points were obtained using capillary apparatus. The IR spectrum was recorded with Perkin-Elmer FT-IR (4000–450 cm^{-1}). The 1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded at 500 MHz, and 125 MHz res-

pectively in $CDCl_3$ (500 MHz FT NMR Spectrometer BRUKER AV III), in TMS as an internal standard. The DEPT135 spectrum was recorded in a standard manner ($\theta = 135$ pulse program). The thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on pre-coated silica plates and the spots were visualized by UV and iodine vapors.

(1-(5-Bromopentyl)indoline-2,3-dione) (15A) :

An orange colored liquid was obtained (71% yield), (hexane : ethyl acetate), R_f : 0.45 (4 : 1 hexane-ethyl acetate); IR (KBr)/ cm^{-1} : 3064, 2941, 2852, 1745, 1728, 1609, 1467, 1356, 701; 1H NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 1.44–1.50 (2H, m), 1.66–1.69 (2H, m), 1.81–1.87 (2H, m), 3.31 (2H, t, J 5 Hz), 3.65 (2H, t, J 5 Hz), 6.88 (1H, d, J 5 Hz), 7.03 (1H, t, J 5 Hz), 7.48–7.50 (1H, m), 7.53–7.56 (1H, m); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 25.34, 26.37, 32.06, 33.46, 39.89, 110.27, 117.44, 123.69, 125.28, 138.52, 150.78, 158.11, 183.47; the ^{13}C DEPT 135 NMR δ : 25.39, 26.44, 32.09, 33.32, 39.95, 110.14, 123.76, 125.52, 138.45; molecular formula $C_{13}H_{14}NO_2Br$; MS m/z 295; elemental analysis : Calcd. (Found) : C, 52.72 (53.71); H, 4.76 (4.39); N, 4.73 (4.93).

(1,1'-(Pentane-1,5-diyl)bis(indoline-2,3-dione)) (15B) :

Obtained as an red colored solid at 24% yield, m.p. 160–162 °C (from hexane-ethyl acetate), R_f : 0.75 (4 : 1 hexane-ethyl acetate); IR (KBr)/ cm^{-1} : 3064, 2941, 2852, 1745, 1728, 1609, 1467, 1356, 701; 1H NMR (500 MHz,

CDCl_3) : δ 1.46–1.52 (2H, m), 1.78–1.84 (4H, m), 3.73 (4H, t, J 10 Hz), 6.93 (2H, d, J 10 Hz), 7.12 (2H, t, J 5 Hz), 7.60–7.63 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 19.15, 21.88, 24.95, 35.02, 105.42, 112.83, 119.04, 120.78, 133.74, 146.02, 153.52, 178.67; the ^{13}C DEPT 135 NMR δ : 23.90, 26.63, 29.71, 39.76, 110.18, 123.81, 125.56, 138.51; MS m/z 362; molecular formula $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$; elemental analysis : Calcd. (Found) : C, 69.60 (70.47); H, 5.01 (4.37); N, 7.73 (7.80).

(6-(5-Bromopentyl)-6H-indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline)
(15AQ) :

Obtained as orange colored solid (83% yield), m.p. 160–162 °C (from hexane-ethyl acetate), R_f : 0.52 (4 : 1 hexane-ethyl acetate); IR (KBr)/ cm^{-1} : 3061, 2930, 2853, 1609, 1581, 1465, 1323, 648; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 1.53–1.59 (2H, m), 1.93–2.01 (4H, m), 3.38 (2H, t, J 5 Hz), 4.51 (2H, t, J 5 Hz), 7.36–7.39 (1H, m), 7.46 (1H, d, J 10 Hz), 7.67–7.71 (2H, m), 7.74–7.77 (1H, m), 8.15 (1H, dd, J 10 Hz), 8.33 (1H, dd, J 10 Hz), 8.52 (1H, d, J 10 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 25.56, 27.60, 32.26, 33.35, 41.12, 109.41, 119.22, 120.97, 123.06, 126.14, 127.76, 128.86, 129.02, 131.17, 138.79, 139.56, 140.53, 144.35, 145.61; the ^{13}C DEPT 135 NMR δ : 22.70, 24.80, 26.98, 28.40, 29.20, 29.36, 33.72, 41.41, 109.55, 120.81, 122.92, 125.98, 127.80, 128.74, 129.17, 131.03; molecular formula $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_3\text{Br}$; MS m/z 367; elemental analysis : Calcd. (Found) : C, 61.97 (62.45); H, 4.93 (5.20); N, 11.41 (12.19).

(1,5-Bis(6H-indolo[2,3-b]quinoxalin-6-yl)pentane)
(15BQ) :

Obtained as orange solid (85% yield), m.p. 160–162 °C (from hexane-ethyl acetate), R_f : 0.61 (4 : 1 hexane-ethyl acetate); IR (KBr)/ cm^{-1} : 3062, 2924, 2854, 1609, 1580, 1468, 1324, 643; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 1.52–1.58 (2H, m), 2.03–2.09 (4H, m), 4.47 (4H, t, J 5 Hz), 7.33–7.39 (4H, m), 7.57–7.619 (2H, m), 7.67–7.75 (4H, m), 8.07 (2H, d, J 10 Hz), 8.33 (2H, d, J 10 Hz), 8.50 (2H, dd, J 10 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 24.60, 28.20, 41.23, 109.41, 119.14, 120.94, 123.04, 126.14, 127.73, 128.85, 129.01, 131.14, 138.74, 139.51, 140.50, 144.38, 145.61; the ^{13}C DEPT 135 NMR δ : 24.60, 28.20, 41.23, 109.41, 120.94, 123.04, 126.14,

127.73, 128.85, 129.00, 131.14; molecular formula $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6$; MS m/z 506; elemental analysis : Calcd. (Found) : C, 78.24 (79.01); H, 5.17 (5.98); N, 16.59 (17.26).

Conclusion

We have successfully designed and synthesized the variegated quinoxaline compounds. Obviously these compounds carry a diverse substitution pattern by choice. This method offers several advantages including simplicity, mild reaction conditions, easy workup, affording the desired products from readily and cheaply available starting materials. Generally there are two steps involved for this process and is applicable to construct a variety of quinoxaline moieties. The determination of anticancer activities for the various quinoxaline compounds which were synthesised are in progress in our laboratory.

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